

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE MECHANICAL AND FLAMMABILITY BEHAVIOUR OF SILICA AND RUBBER NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In the current work, an experimental study of the mechanical and flammability behaviour of silica and rubber nanocomposites was conducted. Single edge notched bend tests were performed to evaluate the fracture energy of the polymers. It was found that the addition of 24 wt.% of core shell rubber (CSR) increased the toughness from 0.19 ± 0.02 kJ/m² to 5.44 ± 0.27 kJ/m². Moreover, flammability testing using a cone heater showed that the time to ignition increases with silica content. This is thought to be primarily caused by an increase in thermal conductivity (or diffusivity) and the formation of a char mass barrier which hinders the flow of pyrolysis gases on the surface of the sample. Hybrid compounds containing both CSR and silica have also been tested and present relatively good mechanical performance as well as reduced flammability due to the presence of nano-silica, with a highest time to ignition of 111 ± 3 s. Poor toughness transfer to CFRP for the hybrid formulations was found, mainly due to the fracture process zone being constrained by inter-laminar spacing. Time to ignition in CFRPs increased compared to the bulk polymer and less damage on the degradation surface was recorded due to the presence of the carbon. The results demonstrate the possibility to manufacture composite materials that are resistant to fire, but still possess outstanding mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of epoxy polymers in engineering is due to their outstanding mechanical properties such as high stiffness and high strength combined with low density which results in high performance lightweight structures. However, the highly cross-linked network structure is responsible for the brittle behaviour. The addition of nanoparticles to toughen the polymer can alleviate this undesired brittleness, typically achieved by the addition of a rubbery phase such as core shell rubber (CSR) particles [1-4]. In most applications, especially in aerospace, epoxies are required to pass fire resistance safety standards as they might be subjected to high temperatures which may promote ignition. Ignition of polymers is dictated by pyrolysis, the irreversible simultaneous physical and chemical change during thermal decomposition of a fuel at elevated temperatures [5]. The pyrolysis into a gaseous fuel is caused by competing chemical reactions which may occur simultaneously or consecutively which are: (a) Chain scission, (b) Chain-stripping and (c) Crosslinking [6,7]. Access to Oxygen is a key variable in the decomposition pathways, which are not limited to outer layers but also occur in depth. Pyrolysis products stemming from the inner layers form bubbles in the softened polymer and migrate to the outside. With a sufficient amount of combustible gas formed, mixing with the surrounding air will occur, forming a critical mixture of fuel which will ignite due to the high temperatures or the presence of a pilot flame [8].

Nano-additives such as silica nano-particles have been shown to promote flame retardant properties even at low additive loading, leading to improvements in thermal properties [9, 10], although leading to a reduction in mechanical properties and especially toughness [11,12].

The demands of increased toughness and improved fire resistance are often antagonistic. Composite systems with simultaneously excellent fire resistance and toughness properties are presented in this work.

2 MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

2.1 Nano-modified bulk epoxy polymers

The samples used were cast from Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) and hardened using isophorone diamine (Vestamin IPD, Evonik Industries, Germany). 18% reactive diluent of 1,6-hexanediol diglycidylether (HDDGE) was added to lower the viscosity and ease processing. Nano-silica with an average diameter of 20 nm (pre-dispersed at 40% in DGEBA, Nanopox F400, Evonik Hanse, Germany) was added at 3 concentrations of 12 wt.%, 24wt.% and 30.5wt.%. The same concentrations were achieved with CSR nano-particles (Albidur, EP2240A, Evonik Hanse, Germany). Two hybrid formulations were created up to saturation. The first one containing 4wt.% CSR, 26.5wt.% NS and the second containing 8wt.% CSR, 22.5wt.% NS. Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN) platelets were also considered as additives. The amount of CRS was kept the same as for the hybrids (4wt.% and 8wt.%), and the hBN was added at 5wt.% and 10wt.% for each, with nano-silica wt.% up to saturation of the particles in the matrix. The ratios of resin to curing agent were adjusted accordingly to maintain a stoichiometric mixture. All formulations are summarised in Table 1.

Sample Code	NS (wt.%)	CSR (wt.%)	HDG GE (wt.%)	hBN (wt.%)
1	0	0	18	0
2	12	0	18	0
3	24	0	18	0
4	30.5	0	18	0
5	0	12	18	0
6	0	24	18	0
7	0	30.5	18	0
H1	26.5	4	18	0
H2	22.5	8	18	0
hBN-1	25	4	18	5
hBN-2	23.5	4	18	10
hBN-3	21	8	18	5
hBN-4	19.5	8	18	10

Table 1: Compositions of bulk polymer samples.

2.2 Nano-modified CFRP composites

CFRP composite laminates were manufactured using the nano-particles modified epoxy matrices described in the previous section. Due to issues during infusion it was decided to change the hardener to allow more time in the mould before gelation point. The hardener, developed by FAC Technology, is an amine blend tailored to give a glass transition temperature of circa 80°C. This implied that the nano-particle addition changed to 30 wt.% for the silica and 26 wt.% and 22 wt.% of silica for the two hybrids. The maximum CSR mixture was not infused as it was too viscous to effectively impregnate the fibre preform even with the new hardener.

To prepare the DCB samples, sixteen plies of biaxial stitched, non-crimp fabric (NFC) were cut into 300x200 mm² rectangles with a cutting knife. A balanced and symmetric layup, [90/0]8s, about the mid-plane was used in order to obtain a '0/0' interface of fibres in the fracture plane. A strip of

polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) film was placed in the mid-plane to initiate a crack in the specimens. For the cone samples, 28 plies of the same fabric was used and cut to 350x150 mm² to achieve the layup of three samples of the desired dimensions of 10x90x90 mm³. A balanced and symmetric layup [90/0]14s was used in order to obtain a '0/0' interface of fibres in the midplane.

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.1 Mechanical testing

Single-edge notched bending (SENB) tests were performed to obtain the fracture toughness K_{Ic} and the fracture energy G_{Ic} , according to ISO-13586 [13] on an Instron 4466. The samples machined in section 3.2.1 were pre-notched to a depth of 6mm using a horizontal mill. The notch was then pre-cracked to a depth of circa 8 mm by tapping the sample with a razor blade cryogenically cooled. The tests were carried out at a constant cross-head displacement rate of 1 mm/min under three-point bending. Ten repeats for each composition were tested. The length of the crack was measured post testing.

Double cantilever beam tests were carried out to measure the inter-laminar fracture energy of CFRP laminates according to ISO-15024 [14] on an Instron 4411. Test specimens of 6x20x200 mm³ were cut from the composite panels and the tests were carried out at a constant cross-head displacement of 5 mm/min. The loads and displacements were recorded, and the crack lengths monitored with a traveling microscope. Five specimens were tested for each formulation.

3.2 Fire testing

The flammability tests were performed using standard cone heater, illustrated in Figure 1. Samples machined into 90x90 mm² plaques of 10 mm thickness were exposed to 30 kW/m² up to the point of spontaneous ignition. The heat flux calibrated before each test using a Huskeflux SBG01 heat flux gauge and the core temperature of the sample was monitored via a K-type thermocouple embedded into the sample at a depth of 5 mm. After ignition, the sample was immediately extinguished in cold water bath of 10 mm depth and, after drying, fixed by encasing it in a low viscosity epoxy resin for microscopic investigation, to preserve and study the fragile skin formed. A schematic of the rig can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Cone heater rig.

The UL94 test rig was built and tested according to [15]. 98% of pure methane was provided at a volumetric flow rate of 105 mL/min \pm 5 mL/min to a Bunsen burner at 1 bar inside the 0.5 m³ chamber. The 50 W methane flame was applied twice for 10 s \pm 0.5 s to specimens, waiting for the flame (or glow) to extinguish between the applications. Depending on the dripping behaviour and self-

sustained combustion times, the samples are then classified on a 'V-' score [15]. A cotton indicator is used to check dripping. Mass data was recorded at 10 Hz to 0.001 g accuracy with an AND FX-200i WP weight scale. A reduction in mass loss would indicate improved flame retardancy. The surface temperature was also recorded with a FLIR A320 IR camera to assess any change in heating rate induced by the additives. Two specimens for each composition were tested. A schematic of the rig can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: UL94 rig.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Mechanical Properties

The fracture properties of samples modified with silica nanoparticles are given in Figure 3. It can be seen that the addition solely of silica nanoparticles results in an increase in fracture toughness up to 24 wt.%. Figure 3 (b) presents the measured fracture energies with increasing addition of CSR particles. The latter are much more effective at toughening the resin than the silica nanoparticles in (a) with a maximum fracture toughness of 5.44 kJ/m² measured for an epoxy system containing 24 wt.% of CSR particles. It can be also seen in Figure 3 that for the hybrid formulations, only a small loss in measured fracture energy is noted over the samples modified with solely CSR nanoparticles. This is a surprising result since for the epoxy nanocomposites modified solely with either CSR particles or silica nanoparticles, a significant reduction in toughening is observed at high rates of particle loading. The exact nature of the synergy in these heavily loaded hybrids is not well understood and is the focus of continuing investigation by the authors.

The samples containing hBN particles were tested and the results can also be seen in Figure 3. A maximum was identified for 5wt.% hBN 8wt.% CSR, 21wt.% NS of 0.64 ± 0.03 kJ/m², which is higher than the best fracture energy registered for nano-silica at 24wt.%. However, it can be observed that the addition of hBN drops the toughness of the sample to less than half of the value without hBN. A maximum difference of 64.9% and 73.7% was calculated between hybrids and corresponding hBN sample with 4wt.% and 8wt.% of CSR respectively. Reasons for this drop could be due to the relatively poor adhesion between the matrix and the hBN particles, which have a relatively large diameter of 5 μ m. It can be noted that adding either 5wt.% or 10wt.% of hBN does not make a considerable difference to the toughness of the particulate composite: increasing to 10wt.% hBN content only slightly decreases fracture energy with respect to 5wt.% hBN (modest 8.7% reduction for the 4wt.% CSR cases and 15.7% reduction for the 8wt.% CSR cases).

Figure 3: Fracture energy versus wt.% for bulk polymers

The mode-I initiation, $G_{Ic,init}$, and propagation, $G_{Ic,prop}$, inter-laminar fracture energies obtained from the DCB tests for the CFRP laminates can be seen in Figure 4. DCB test results agree extremely well with the experimental values measured from SENB testing. From both tests, it is evident that the contribution of silica to toughness was minimal. For the hybrids, a big overall decrease in toughness is observed despite the presence of CSR: a decrease in 73.85 % and 68.53% respectively is registered compared to their bulk counterparts. The reason is that the toughness of the CFRP will increase proportionally to the toughness of the resin up to the point where the size of the deformation zone is roughly equal to the inter-fibre spacing, suggesting that the much stiffer fibres prevent the growth of the fracture process zone in the epoxy matrix [12].

Figure 4: Fracture energy versus wt.% of silica for CFRP laminates

4.2 Fire retardant properties

Time to ignition (TTI) results can be seen in Figure 5. Figure 5 (b) shows that the time to ignition decreases for increasing rubber content, as expected. The hybrid compositions showed relatively better fire resistance due to the presence of nano-silica with a highest time to ignition of 111 ± 3 s. Ignition is clearly further delayed with the addition of hBN: with just 10% of hBN added, the time to ignition is raised to a max of 1785 ± 5 s, and almost doubled with respect to the baseline value of 96 ± 2 s. The results in (a) reveal that the addition of silica nanoparticles increases the time to ignition as well as the core temperatures. This is in agreement with previous measurements by Roenner et al. [4]. They explained that this increase in flammability resistance was due to two separate effects working in

parallel: (1) an increase in thermal diffusivity which leads to an increase in core temperature and thermal gradients through the sample, while the surface temperature is reduced, delaying the time to ignition, (2) a formation of a char mass barrier leading to the formation of an almost continuous skin. Roenner et al. explain that the char formation hinders the flow of flammable pyrolysis gases, less pyrolysate is released into the environment, delaying the formation of a flammable mixture above the sample, and hence ignition.

Figure 5: Time to ignition versus wt.%

The heat flux for the CFRP laminates testing was raised to 35 kW/m² in order to reach critical heat flux. This was necessary because for a 30 kW/m² heat flux, the radiation provided was not sufficient to cause autoignition in the CFRP samples as the carbon fibres (not flammable) are well dispersed in the matrix, in proportions defined by the fibre volume fraction. The TTI results can be seen in Figure 6. Comparing Figure 6 to Figure 5 (a), it can be observed that the addition of carbon fibres in the laminates has raised the time to ignition from 96 ± 2 s of the bulk polymer to 132 ± 10 s for the 0wt.% resin, and from 114 ± 6 s to 187 ± 27 s for the 30.5wt.% NS case. On the hybrids side, an increase of 39.3% is recorded for the 4wt.% CSR, 26.5wt.% NS, and a 7.5% decrease for the 8wt.% CSR, 22.5wt.% NS hybrid compared to their bulk polymers.

Figure 6: Time to ignition versus wt.%

The surfaces of the cone samples have also been analysed and are showed in Figures 7. Firstly, a clear trend over the samples' surfaces can be observed based on their composition: it can be seen that compared to the baseline (a), the addition of silica allowed the formation of a thicker skin. In fact, it can be seen that (b) shows a more exposed and fragile char surface compared to (c). It was observed

that before ignition, the samples started boiling and rising, creating relatively big gas bubbles on the surface. As the samples were heated, a thin skin formed which was detached from the polymer matrix by the pressure of the pyrolysis gases [16]. As the concentration of nano-silica increased, the skin became thicker and more continuous with less exit spots for the gases. At 30.5wt.% of silica, a strong structure was formed (Figure 6 (d)) which the pyrolysis gases ceased to inflate and above which the sample did not collapse when cooled in the water bath. It was also observed that samples corresponding to 24wt.% and 30.5wt.% of nano-silica self-extinguished. On the other hand, a much worse surface condition can be observed for (e), (f) and (g), which correspond to 12wt.%, 24wt.% and 30.5wt.% of CSR respectively. The samples showed increased degree of degradation and deformation over the entire surface area, in combination with quicker ignition times. Moreover, the samples quickly started to melt.

The surface for the hybrid samples is shown in (h) and (i) an intermediate behaviour was observed. A better surface skin can be seen when the nano-silica percentage is higher, but in general both samples showed some surface roughness due to the rubber.

Finally, the hBN samples tested are shown in Figure 8. All samples self-extinguished within 2 minutes, with the last small flames being on the perimeter of the sample, corresponding to the only exit spots for the gases. More uniform surface charring can be seen for 10wt.% hBN samples (b) and (d) compared to the 5wt.% hBN for the same CSR composition in (a) and (c). It was noticed that the flame ignited on a more reduced area and that the sample under the surface was neither damaged nor deformed/melted, in comparison to the CSR samples. The samples containing hBN seemed to form a more effective, but thinner, 'protective skin' on the surface than the silica only samples.

Figure 6: Top view of sample surfaces after ignition in the cone: (a) 0wt.%; (b) 12wt.% NS; (c) 24wt.% NS; (d) 30.5wt.% NS; (e) 12wt.% CSR; (f) 24wt.% CSR; (g) 30.5wt.% CSR; (h) 4wt.% CSR, 26.5wt.% NS; (i) 8wt.% CSR, 22.5wt.%

Figure 8: Left: (a) 5wt.% hBN, 4wt.% CSR, 25wt.% NS ; (b) 10wt.% hBN, 4wt.% CSR, 23.5wt.% NS; (c) 5wt.% hBN, 8wt.% CSR, 21wt.% NS; (d) 10wt.% hBN, 8wt.% CSR, 19.5wt.% NS
 Right: (a) 0wt.%; (b) 30.5wt.% NS; (C) 4wt.% CSR, 26.5wt.% NS; (d) 8wt.% CSR, 22.5wt.% NS

In the UL94 test, improvements in fire retardancy existed but were less pronounced and less quantitative. All the samples ignited, dripped and did not self-extinguish after application of the flame and hence failing the V-rating, showing that silica and hBN are not sufficient to pass the flammability test. The samples continued burning and the afterflame and afterglow times could not be measured. A discrepancy between cone and UL94 results had already been shown in literature, for which the improvement seen in the cone does not translate well over the UL94 test [9, 17, 18].

The CSR samples were not tested since they presented reduced flame retardancy behaviour during the cone heater experiment and hence were deemed not to be able to pass the UL94 rating. This was the case for the hybrids too, as they contain CSR.

The specimens containing hBN were tested, but failed to pass the rating, similarly to the silica samples. It was noted however that the specimens took longer to ignite when the flame was applied for 10 s, and, whilst still not self-extinguishing, they took longer to burn and consume. Moreover, it was observed that the flame was much more flickering and emitting incandescent particles as well as popping noises, compared to the silica-only flame. The dripping of material was also very different, in the silica case falling continuously on the weight scale at small amounts while for the hBN cases falling on the scale in few bigger chunks, the material being more capable of still holding together despite the burning.

4.3 Summary

Based on all previous results on both mechanical and flame retardant properties, a plot of fracture energy versus time to ignition was made and can be seen in Figure 9. The points in blue represent CSR, whilst the silica nano-composites are represented in dark violet, as per previous graphs in this paper. Plotting these two properties with respect to one another gives a clear indication that higher performance/optimum compounds are situated in the top right corner of the graph. Trends can be observed when using different weights of CSR, silica and hBN, and a pay off between toughness and fire resistance will determine an optimum point for both criteria.

Figure 8: TTI versus fracture energy for all compositions

5 MICROSCOPY

5.1 Scanning electron microscopy

The fracture surface of the SENB samples were analysed using the scanning electron microscope (SEM). Silica concentration of 24wt.% can be seen in Figure 10 (a). Some voids are present (highlighted in light green) as some particles seem to debond. The presence of voids confirms the results obtained in Figure 3 (a) for which a peak in toughness with silica addition was observed at 24wt.%. For a maximum 30.5wt.% silica packing, the fracture surface can be seen in Figure 10 (b). In this case, a very different fracture surface is observed. The interparticle distance is so reduced that no space for void growth is available. The microstructure explains its toughness performance, which resulted in a drop of 53.55 % compared to the 24wt.% NS formulation.

The 24wt.% CSR SEM imaging can be seen in Figure 10 (c). In this case, the voids start to lose shape, not having space to grow uniformly. The majority of particles do however still cavitate and this translates into good toughness behaviour observed in Figure 3 (b), for which the peak corresponds to this CSR formulation. For the 30.5wt.% CSR (saturation) a very distorted surface layer is obtained (Figure 10 (d)). No more concentric voids are able to develop due to the limited space. This compromises the toughening mechanisms of the rubber, hence resulting in poor mechanical performance and a drop in fracture energy, as indicated by the SENB testing results.

The two hybrid formulations were also analysed and the 4wt.% CSR 26.5wt.% fracture surface can be seen in Figure 10 (e). Good dispersion of both the silica and CSR is observed. Despite the limited space due to particle saturation, the smaller size of the silica nano-particles allows the rubber to still cavitate and the voids to grow, as the silica does not seem to affect the toughening mechanism of the CSR. The surface layer of the 8wt.% CSR 22.5wt.% NS hybrid is not shown but presented very similar behaviour.

Figure 10 (f) shows the fracture surface for the first hBN formulation, composed of 5wt.% hBN, 4wt.% CSR, 25wt.% NS. The bigger hBN platelets can be seen and their hexagonal shape is deformed and distorted during fracture. Moreover, it can be noted that despite the CSR and silica being able to uniformly distribute in the matrix, the hBN seems to agglomerate in groups at the surface. The fractured hBN platelets seem to stack in all directions and appear completely smooth: no particle seems to stick on their surface, but only in between them to bind them. The voids of the CSR particles in between the platelets are smaller compared to the ones in the matrix due to the limited space.

Figure 10: SEM images of SENB fracture surfaces

5.2 Energy dispersive x-ray spectrometry

EDX analysis was performed to measure the relative presence of elements at different locations of the degradation surface of the cone samples. The hBN-1 and hBN-2 samples were analysed, as they contain both Boron and Silica, whose quantities, together with Carbon and Oxygen, are investigated. The samples were encased into a low viscosity resin and then cut in the middle and polished using diamond suspension down to a 0.25 μm finish.

Figure 11 shows low magnification (x35) SEM images and EDX results in the areas investigated for (a) 5wt% hBN, 4wt.% CSR, 25wt.% NS, and (b) 10wt.% hBN, 4wt.% CSR, 23.5wt.% NS. Four spectra for each sample were analysed: at 3 mm , 2 mm , 1 mm from the degradation surface and then

on the degradation surface itself. On the latter, the bubbles stemming from pyrolysis can be seen migrating to the outside, forming a porous structure. A thicker degradation surface was observed for the second sample. A plot of the amounts of elements with respect to the spectrum position can be seen on the right hand side of Figure 11. The samples were coated with gold and hence high amounts of this element were expected. The results indicate that the relative amounts of Silica, Carbon and Oxygen increase significantly towards the surface. This implies that a silica char mass barrier has formed on the degradation surface. However, Boron was not detected at the surface, in contrast with early thoughts outlined in Section 4.2 that an additional hBN skin might be formed. This was an unexpected result and future work will concentrate on understanding this behaviour.

Figure 11: SEM images showing the areas where the EDX was applied on a (a) 5wt.% hBN, 4wt.% CSR, 25wt.% NS, and (b) 10wt.% hBN, 4wt.% CSR, 23.5wt.% sample after degradation in the cone. The right hand side shows the relative signals of Silica, Carbon, Boron and Oxygen.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Simultaneously tough and fire resistant epoxy nanocomposites have been manufactured by heavily loading the epoxy matrix with silica nanoparticles. The toughening effects of rubber particles are found to be far greater than for silica nanoparticles, in accordance with literature. The potential to create hybrid nanocomposites that are an order of magnitude tougher than existing epoxy resins as well as demonstrating vastly improved fire resistance is outlined and presented outstanding results. The hybrid compositions showed that their toughness is dominated by the CSR particles and that their fire resistance is dominated by the presence of nano-silica, with a highest time to ignition of 111 ± 3 s.

The propagation inter-laminar fracture energies of the CFRPs were far greater than those compared to the values of the corresponding bulk epoxy polymers. This arises from additional fibre-induced toughening mechanisms. However, poor toughness transfer to CFRP for the hybrid formulation was obtained, due to limitation of fracture process zone by the inter-laminar spacing. The time to ignition in CFRP increased with silica content and the degradation surface damage of the cone samples was reduced compared to their bulk.

New formulations involving a mixture of CSR, silica and hBN have been tested. It was noted that the presence of hBN did not translate fully in toughness performance, which was shown through SEM imaging. Time to ignition was raised considerably: with just 10% of hBN added, the TTI reached 178 ± 5 s, almost doubling with respect to the baseline value of 96 ± 2 s. UL94 tests showed less dripping

compared to the specimens containing just silica. EDX analysis recorded the presence of silica on the degradation surface but not Boron, raising the hypothesis that a more complex silica surface layer mechanism is taking place. The nature of the synergy between these two elements has not been reported in current literature yet and is the topic of further investigation by the authors.

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